

SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC NEEDS, THEIR COMPOSITION AND METHODS OF SATISFACTION

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Abstract. *The article describes the effectiveness of the measures taken to increase the national economy at the expense of socio-economic needs, their composition and methods of satisfaction. At the same time, we will consider ways to meet the needs.*

Keywords: *socio-economic, target, political, TREE, EPA, program, service-disabled.*

Promoting the availability of information on the socio-economic aspects of climate change and improving the integration of socio-economic information into impact and vulnerability assessments.

For communities all over the world, socio-economic and natural conditions have changed over time, in some cases quite dramatically. As a result of these changes, vulnerability to climate change and the effectiveness of adaptation to it were affected as well. These shifts in the socio-economic structure of societies continue to pose risks and challenges to a great number of people. For example, increased population growth may place more people and property at risk from increased frequency or intensity of extreme climate events. On the other hand, economic growth and development may increase the wealth and the capacity of a community to withstand and adjust to future changes, thus reducing the measured impact compared to current circumstances.

Preliminary socio-economic

Determining whether TREE is going to be a useful method to use in a particular context is an important first step. This is not the in-depth analysis you will use to develop the details of a TREE program, but a high-level scan to see if the right elements are in place for TREE to be relevant. Key things to consider are:

Does the country have relevant target groups and economic/geographic areas that are suitable for the method?

- This means populations that are chronically poor, living in areas with limited formal economic opportunities and few services.
- There are also potential risks associated with these conditions: stability, security, and potential for significant climate impacts. Areas may be post-conflict or have been devastated by a natural disaster.

What is the legal, political and institutional context?

- Does the country or region have a development or poverty reduction plan that includes objectives for rural economic development?
- Are there any legal barriers that would limit the potential for development of employment, self-employment or cooperatives for some or all potential beneficiaries (for example, women's access to title, citizenship requirements)
- Are there existing or potential champions for the approach at the local and higher levels in government or community, including religious and social organizations? Conversely, is there potential for opposition from any such group?
- Are there training and business support service provider systems, institutions and other

providers, and do they currently provide any services to rural areas and/ or the intended beneficiaries?

- Are there tensions, divisions or conflicts that could be reduced or resolved by improved jobs and livelihoods in selected communities?

Is it likely that local actors will be able to take on full responsibility for TREE?

- Part of TREE's approach is to build the capacity of local actors, so they may not be immediately ready, but the longer-term potential should be there.
- Consider how other programs and projects in the area have fared, and what expectations a TREE approach has
- If TREE is implemented in fragile contexts, conduct a peace and conflict analysis.

Is there potential for national and donor-based financing?

- This could include donor support specifically for a TREE program, using the TREE method to develop services under national / donor funds intended for rural economic development or training, allocation of national training funds, or a combination of sources.
- If external or short-term funding is available, what are the longer-term options for sustainability?

Based on these factors, consider whether a TREE program is likely to be both welcomed and have potential for success.

Note that while some environments may not be suitable for long term sustainability/adoption of TREE yet, the method can be used to develop short term interventions in crisis/post-crisis situations, adapted as needed.

Sources of information for this preliminary socio-economic/context scan include:

- National or local economic development plans
- National poverty reduction or other plans
- ILO Decent Work Country Program (DWCP) plans and reports
- ILO and UN country office information
- Peace and conflict analyses
- Employer and Worker specialists in the region
- Information from related programs and projects in the country (skills, cooperatives, jobs etc.)

A short report on the socio-economic/context scan serves as an initial decision and planning document for the development of a TREE program.

Socioeconomic Programs for Small Businesses

Small Business Set-Asides – This program requires agencies to limit competition on certain contracts to qualified small businesses so that small firms do not have to compete with large ones for the same contracts. However, because the law requires the Government to buy at competitive prices, contracts are set aside when two small businesses are expected to submit offers to ensure adequate competition. SBA establishes size standards that determine a firm's eligibility to offer on set-asides. These standards are established on an industry-by-industry basis, using dollar volume of sales or number of employees, to determine eligibility.

Small Disadvantaged Business Program – For the purpose of improving and stimulating this small business segment, EPA established a realistic Department-wide goal for the award of contracts to small business concerns owned and controlled by socially and economically disadvantaged individuals. OSBP is also responsible for the Department's program to encourage

greater economic opportunity for minority entrepreneurs. To implement these requirements, goals are established for award of contracts to small disadvantaged businesses.

If your business is (a) at least 51 percent owned by one or more individuals who are both socially and economically disadvantaged and (b) managed and controlled by one or more such individuals, you are eligible to participate under this program. Economically or socially disadvantaged individuals for government procurement purposes include African Americans, Hispanic Americans, Native Americans, (American Indians, Eskimos, Aleuts, or Native Hawaiians): Asian Pacific Americans (persons with origins from Japan, China, the Philippines, Vietnam, Korea, Samoa, Guam, U.S. Trust Territory of the Pacific Islands, Northern Mariana Islands, Laos, Cambodia, or Taiwan, Asian Indian Americans (persons with origins from India, Pakistan or Bangladesh); and members of other groups designated from time to time by the SBA under 13 CFR 124.105(d).

8(a) Program – OSBP promotes increased utilization of small businesses owned and controlled by socially and economically disadvantaged individuals certified under the SBA Section 8(a) Program.

Section 8(a) of the Small Business Act, as amended, authorizes SBA to contract for goods and services with Federal agencies. SBA then subcontracts actual performance of the work to socially and economically disadvantaged small businesses which have been certified by SBA as eligible to receive these contracts. The major advantage of this program is that it provides Government contracts on a noncompetitive basis to socially and economically disadvantaged small businesses. SBA also offers managerial, technical, and financial support to participating firms.

The purpose of the 8(a) Program is to:

- Foster business ownership by individuals who are socially and economically disadvantaged.
- Promote the competitive viability of these firms by providing contract, technical, and management assistance.
- Expand acquisition opportunities for these firms.

To be eligible for the 8(a) Program, a concern must qualify as a small business at least 51 percent owned by a U.S. citizen who is determined by SBA to be socially and economically disadvantaged and are subject to a fixed program participation term.

Woman-Owned Small Business Program – In response to the need to aid and stimulate women's business enterprises, this advocacy program directs acquisition officials to take appropriate action to facilitate, preserve, and strengthen women's business enterprises and to ensure full participation by women in the free enterprise system. Appropriate action includes the award of prime contracts and subcontracts and counseling of women-owned businesses. "Women-owned small businesses" means small business concerns that are at least 51 percent owned, controlled, and operated by women who are United States citizens. OSBP is responsible for negotiating annual goals with EPA acquisition officials to increase Federal prime contracts with women-owned small businesses.

Service-Disabled Veteran Owned Small Business Program – Public Law 106-50 established a contracting goal for Federal agencies to award 3% of prime contracts to service-disabled veteran-owned small businesses (SDVOSBs). In addition, large Prime Contractors have SDVOSB subcontracting goals.

EPA's strategy for contracting with Service-Disabled Veteran-Owned Small Businesses demonstrates our commitment to maximize opportunities for veteran-owned small businesses in our Federal contracting. The strategy includes:

- Reserving contracts exclusively for service-disabled veteran businesses;
- Encouraging and facilitating participation by service-disabled veteran businesses in competitions for award of Agency contracts;
- Encouraging Agency contractors to subcontract with service-disabled veteran businesses and actively monitoring and evaluating Agency contractors' efforts to do so;
- Training Agency personnel on applicable law and policies relating to participation of service-disabled veteran businesses in Federal contracting;
- Disseminating information to service-disabled veteran businesses that would assist these businesses in participating in awards of Agency contracts; and
- Holding special outreach sessions for service-disabled veteran businesses.

To qualify for the SDVOSB program, a business must be a small business by SBA size standards, and it must be owned and controlled by one or more service-disabled veterans (0 - 100% disability rating).

HubZone Program - A "HUBZone" is an area that is located in one or more of the following:

- a qualified census tract (as defined in section 42(d)(5)(C)(i)(I) of the Internal Revenue Code of 1986);
- a qualified "non-metropolitan county" (as defined in section 143(k)(2)(B) of the Internal Revenue Code of 1986) with a median household income of less than 80 percent of the State median household income or with an unemployment rate of not less than 140 percent of the statewide average, based on US Department of Labor recent data; or
- lands within the boundaries of federally recognized Indian reservations.

To qualify as a HubZone business, a small business must meet all of the following criteria to qualify for the HUBZone program:

- it **must** be located in a "historically underutilized business zone" or HUBZone.
- it **must** be owned and controlled by one or more US Citizens, and
- at least 35% of its employees **must** reside in a HUBZone.

The US Small Business Administration (SBA) regulates and implements the HUBZone program. Also, SBA:

- determines which businesses are eligible to receive HUBZone contracts,
- maintains a listing of qualified HUBZone small businesses that Federal agencies can use to locate vendors,
- adjudicates protests of eligibility to receive HUBZone contracts, and
- reports to the Congress on the program's impact on employment and investment in HUBZone areas.

The social and economic opportunities we have, such as good schools, stable jobs, and strong social networks are foundational to achieving long and healthy lives. For example, employment provides income that shapes choices about housing, education, child care, food, medical care, and more. In contrast, unemployment limits these choices and the ability to accumulate savings and assets that can help cushion in times of economic distress.

Social and economic factors are not commonly considered when it comes to health, yet strategies to improve these factors can have an even greater impact on health over time than those traditionally associated with health improvement, such as strategies to improve health behaviors.

Across the nation, there are meaningful differences in social and economic opportunities for residents in communities that have been cut off from investments or have experienced discrimination. These gaps disproportionately affect people of color – especially children and youth.

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